

A Study of Five-Factor Model of Personality and Employee Counter Work Behavior Among Staff of Selected NGOs

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Abstract

Employee counter work behavior is influenced by various factors including personality and environmental factors. In the present study, the objective was to test the influence of personality dimensions based on the Five-Factor model of personality and employee counter work behavior. Through the convenience sampling approach, primary data is collected from the staff of five selected NGOs (n=170) utilizing the survey method. The method of analysis was structural equation modeling using the AMOS software. Reliability is assessed using the Cronbach alpha and composite reliability; while, convergent validity is established using the Average Variance Extracted; and discriminant validity using the Fornell & Larcker criteria. Coefficient indicates that extraversion and conscientiousness dimension bring negative influence on employee counter work behavior; neuroticism and openness bring positive influence on employee counter work behavior, and mixed results were found for agreeableness dimension. Results imply that personality is an important predictor of employee counter work behavior and may be used in candidate screening during the recruitment & selection process.

Keywords: Personality, Counter Work Behavior, NGOs, SEM.

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Introduction

Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) plays an important role in development efforts of developing countries. However, despite some good work, NGOs sector is hit by allegations of corruption, theft, and exploitation of vulnerable groups. Take example of Oxfam which is a famous British charity is finding its public image deteriorating as news about its staff sexually abusing the vulnerable groups during a mission in in Haiti and Chad. Another scandal is related to Blue Helmets. Accordingly, the UN received at least 70 complaints related to Blue Helmet staff in the domain of financial corruption and sexual abuse. Mostly, these negative behaviors such as theft, sabotage, and abuse are studied under the label of ‘employee counter work behavior’ (Spector & Fox, 2005). Studies in this domain focused on understanding what causes employees to involve in counter work behavior. Some studies pointed out the personality related factors (Bolton, Becker, & Barber, 2010; O’Neil, Lewis, & Carswell, 2011); while, other focused on environmental factors (Bakker, Van der Zeek, Lewig, & Dollard, 2002; Bunk & Magley, 2013; Kelloway, Francis, Prosser, & Cameron, 2010). In this study, it is investigated that what is the relationship between personality traits of employees and their counterproductive work behavior in the context of the social sector or NGO’s.

1.1 Problem Statement

According to a report, every year, organizations suffer loss of US\$ 200 billion due to the employee counter work behavior (Penny, 2002). Similarly, in NGO s sector, it is estimated that 40 per cent of developmental aid goes in corruption and not reached to its intended beneficiaries (UN, 2012). Another estimate by UNDP reported that funds lost to corruption are almost 20 to 40 per cent of official development assistance (Integritas, 2016). The context of the study is NGO sector. This sector is experiencing some counter work behavior and complaints include theft of funds and physical goods, sabotage and involvement in other illegitimate practices. In such a situation, it is very important that NGO based organizations must take suitable steps to curb such counter work behavior. Sole reliance on the organizational policies and procedure is not enough, and the organization must take efforts beyond. One way to curb this is to identify such individuals during the recruitment and selection process which can help in reducing the chances of counter work behavior later on. For this reason, this study is motivated to measure the relationship between counter work behavior and employee counter work behavior.

1.2 Research Objective

To measure the effects of the Five-Factor model of personality dimensions and employee counter work behavior.

1.3 Research Gap

The research so far suggests that there is an influence of employee's personality on staff counter work behavior (e.g. Berry, Ones, & Sackett, 2007; Kozako, Safin, & Rahim, 2013; Penney, David, & Witt, 2011; Salgado, 2002). However, mostly, these studies conducted in the Western context but not in developing countries context. Therefore, the contribution of this study is to add the empirical work on selected NGOs of developing countries context.

1.4 Significance of the Study

The theoretical significance of the present study is that its findings are developing countries specific and thus fill this valid literature gap. The practical significance of the study is that the managers of the NGOs in the developing countries can use the findings in order to better predict staff counter work behavior. The findings can also be used during the recruitment and selection process by NGOs. The findings can be used by the social sector and relevant sectors such as services sector and government or public sector organizations.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Personality- an Introduction

McAdam and Olson (2010) describe personality as a set of individual differences that are affected by the development of an individual; values, attitudes, personal memories, social relationships, habits, and skills. Another way to look at the personality is that it blends of characteristics that make a person unique (Weinberg & Gould, 1999).

2.2 The Five-Factor Models of Personality

The Five-Factor Model personality consist of five factors of personality and is one of the leading model for understanding individual psychology (John, Naumann, & Sotro, 2008). The nature of the five factors of personality is such that it can be observed using some behavioral indicators. Initially, researchers come up with a large number of personality traits but with the passage of time, these were reduced and eventually the Five-Factor model of personality emerged. Based on extensive studies from various International context, the model showed good validity and theoretical soundness (Saucier, 2009; Benet-Martinez & John, 1998).

Extraversion is the first main dimension in this Five-factor model and is based on characteristics including excitement, outgoing, dominant, seeks adventure, self-confident, and socially active (Bakker et al 2002). Other characteristics of extraversion include talkative, assertive, sociable, and outgoing. According to Jensen-Campbell and Malcolm (2006), employees who score higher on extraversion dimension are experiencing less anger compare to those who have a lower score on this dimension. Individuals who score low on extraversion dimension are introvert and remains less socially active (Salgado, 2002).

Agreeableness is the second personality dimension and is about cooperation and compassion (Bakker et al 2002). Individuals with higher score on agreeable dimension tends to show more courtesy, empathic behavior, caring, and compassion. In other words, such individuals are friendly, forgiving, trusting, flexible, and cooperative.

Conscientiousness dimension is the third factor in the Five-Factor model and is about well-disciplined, organization, and routine orientation (Bakker et al 2002). Such individuals also possess the characteristics of planful, delay gratification, and goal-directed (Roberts, Jackson, Fayard, Edmonds, & Meints, 2009). Those individuals who score low on this dimension exhibit greater irregularity in their behavior and tends to avoid set routine.

Neuroticism is the fourth dimension in the Five-Factor personality model and is about emotional stability. If an individual score high on neuroticism so it means such individuals are not emotionally stable (McShane & Glinow, 2017). In other words, neuroticism and emotional stability are opposite to each other and refer to the same concept. Practically speaking, individuals with a high score on neuroticism is not very suitable since such individuals can exhibit extreme behavior within an organization (Kappe & Flier, 2010).

Openness to experience is the fifth and last dimension of the Five-Factor personality model. This dimension is about being creative, imaginative, original, and experiment with new ideas (Bakker et al 2002). Other characteristics of individuals who score on openness to experience dimension include aesthetically sensitive, curious, creative, and being creative (McShane & Glinow, 2017). Individuals who score low on this dimension tend to follow a pre-specified routine and avoid new ideas (McShane & Glinow, 2017).

2.3 Counter Work Behavior (CWB)

CWB is about volitional behavior which harms or tends to harm members of the organization or organization itself (Spector & Fox, 2005). Other relevant terms of counter work behavior include counterproductive behavior (Omar, Vaamonde, & Delgado, 2013); and deviant behavior

(Robinson & Bennett, 1995). According to Conlon, Meyer, and Nowakowski (2005) counter work behavior is deliberately performed by individuals with the intention to harm the organization, its people, and its assets. It can be said that counter work behavior is highly negative for the organization as it carries financial and human costs (Bunk & Magley, 2013). Spector and Fox (2005) suggest that the dimensions of counter work behavior include withdrawal, theft, sabotage, production deviance, and abuse. In terms of level, some counter work behavior can be minor levels such as displaying simple aggression; whereas, at a higher level it can be something like revenge or retaliation. From an organizational perspective, understanding which personality factors lead to counterwork behavior is important. It is important since understanding of factors predicting employee counter work behavior can be helpful for curbing such behavior. Generally speaking, the factors causes counter work behavior can be personality related as well as external environmental factors (Kelloway et al 2010). The focus of the study is testing Five-factor model of personality and its relationship with employee counter work behavior.

2.4 The Influence of the Five-Factor Model of Personality on Employee Counter Work Behavior

According to Penney et al (2011), the personality of an individual is an important predictor of behavior including workplace behavior. Previously several studies conducted on this topic show that there is some degree of influence of personality characteristics on employee counter work behavior or deviant behavior. For instance, a meta-analysis by Berry et al (2007) shows that dimensions including neuroticism, agreeableness, and conscientiousness are associated with employee counter work behavior. Another meta-analysis performed by Salgado (2002) reported that counter work behavior is influenced by the personality profile of individual employees especially the dimensions of agreeableness and conscientiousness. Kozako et al (2013) study was about personality traits and hotel employees' counter work behavior in the Malaysian context. Results were that agreeableness is negatively influencing staff counter work behavior; while, openness to experience and neuroticism positively influence staff counter work behavior. Jensen-Campbell and Malcolm (2006) study was also about personality traits and employee counter work behavior. Results were that extraversion dimension is associated with employee counter work behavior. Bolton et al (2010) study also established a connection between agreeableness and staff counter work behavior. O'Neill et al (2011) study also established that there is a negative connection between agreeableness dimension of personality and employee counter

work behavior. Conscientiousness dimension of personality is also found to be negatively associated with employee counter work behavior as reported in studies such as O’Neill et al (2011); and Witt, Andrews, and Carlson (2004). The study by Bolton et al (2010) also reported a positive association between openness to experience and employee counter work behavior. In sum, previous studies indicate that personality traits based on the Five-Factor model of personality are associated with employee counter work behavior. Moreover, the nature of relationships based on literature is such that extraversion, neuroticism, and openness to experience are positively associated with employee counter work behavior; while conscientiousness and agreeableness dimension are negatively associated with employee counter work behavior. One theory which can be used to explain the relationship between personality traits and employee counter work behavior is social learning theory. The theory is based on the work of Bandura and explains that individuals learn from their social environment (Bandura, 1977). Building on the social learning theory, Priesmuth, Arnaud, and Schminke (2013) suggest that individuals unsocial and counter behavior is the result of learning from the environment and employees replicate such counter behavior in some suitable time in future. Based on the literature review and social learning theory, we propose the following hypothetical model.

Figure 1: Theoretical Model

Source: Author compilation

In this model, the Five-Factor model of personality including extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness are independent variables. Employee counter work behavior is a dependent variable that is based on five dimensions including sabotage, withdrawals, deviance, theft, and abuse. Hypotheses of the study are presented below;

H1: Five-Factor model of personality is significantly related to sabotage dimension

H1a: Extraversion is significantly related to sabotage dimension.

H1b: Agreeableness is significantly related to sabotage dimension.

H1c: Conscientiousness is significantly related to sabotage dimension.

H1d: Neuroticism is significantly related to sabotage dimension.

H1e: Openness is significantly related to sabotage dimension.

H2: Five-Factor model of personality is significantly related to withdrawal dimension.

H2a: Extraversion is significantly related to withdrawal dimension.

H2b: Agreeableness is significantly related to withdrawal dimension.

H2c: Conscientiousness is significantly related to withdrawal dimension.

H2d: Neuroticism is significantly related to withdrawal dimension.

H2e: Openness is significantly related to withdrawal dimension.

H3: Five-Factor model of personality is significantly related to deviance dimension.

H3a: Extraversion is significantly related to deviance dimension.

H3b: Agreeableness is significantly related to deviance dimension.

H3c: Conscientiousness is significantly related to deviance dimension.

H3d: Neuroticism is significantly related to deviance dimension.

H3e: Openness is significantly related to deviance dimension.

H4: Five-Factor model of personality is significantly related to theft dimension.

H4a: Extraversion is significantly related to theft dimension.

H4b: Agreeableness is significantly related to theft dimension.

H4c: Conscientiousness is significantly related to theft dimension.

H4d: Neuroticism is significantly related to theft dimension.

H4e: Openness is significantly related to theft dimension.

H5: Five-Factor model of personality is significantly related to abuse dimension.

H5a: Extraversion is significantly related to abuse dimension.

H5b: Agreeableness is significantly related to abuse dimension.

H5c: Conscientiousness is significantly related to abuse dimension.

H5d: Neuroticism is significantly related to abuse dimension.

H5e: Openness is significantly related to abuse dimension.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

In terms of research design, the present study is cross-sectional and is quantitative in nature. Quantitative design is chosen because of its matching with the title of study.

3.2 Population and Sampling

For this study, the focus was five selected NGOs operating in the social sector and working in projects related to capacity development, women's rights issues, internally displaced citizens, and victims of natural disasters. These NGOs were selected on convenience basis. The nature of these NGOs are such that they are local NGOs and author had access to these NGOs based on some consultancy work to these NGOs. The unit of analysis is individual staff member. Total of 335 questionnaires were distributed among the employees of selected NGOs using the convenient sampling method. Total of 170 respondents returned the questionnaire making response rate of 50.74 per cent.

3.3 Data Collection Measure

For data collection, the survey method is used. Our survey is based on previously developed measures. The Five-Factor model of personality is adapted from John and Srivastava (1999). The measure contains 8 items for extraversion, 9 items for agreeableness, 9 items for conscientiousness, 8 items for neuroticism, and 10 items for openness. The questionnaire for counter work behavior is adapted from Spector, Fox, Penney, Bruursema, Goh, and Kessler (2006). In total, there are 32 items for counter work. Dimension wise, there are 3 items for sabotage, 4 items for withdrawal, 3 items for production deviance, 5 items for theft, and 17 items for abuse dimension.

3.4 Data Collection

Data is collected using the survey method which was physically distributed and collected back from the social sector employees working in various projects run by five selected NGOs.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

We followed the academic ethical norms. Common ethical issues were no deception to the survey participants, no use of force for participation in

the survey, no harm to the participants, and maintenance of confidentiality and privacy of the survey participants. We took reasonable measures to address these ethical issues.

4 Results

Table 1: Demographic

		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	138	81.2
	Female	32	18.8
Age	18 to 25 Years	20	11.8
	25 to 35 Years	81	47.6
	35 to 45 Years	59	34.7
	Above 45 Years	10	5.9
Role	Program Manager	15	8.8
	Program Coordinator	24	14.1
	Project Assistant	15	8.8
	Monitoring & Evaluation Officer	24	14.1
	Field Officer	23	13.5
	Field Worker	22	12.9
	Support Staff	25	14.7
	Others	22	12.9

Source: Author compilation

Table 1 present the demographic details. The study is based on 170 staff members of social sector organizations. There were 138 males and 32 females participated in the study. In terms of age, 20 were in the age group of 18 to 25 years; 81 were in 25 to 35 years; 59 were in the age group of 35 to 45 years, and 10 were above 45 years' age. In terms of job role, 15 were various program managers; 24 were program coordinators; 15 were program assistant; 24 were monitoring & evaluation officers; 23 were field officers; 22 were field workers; 25 were support staff; and 22 were others category.

Table 2: Reliability, Validity, and Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted	Mean	S.D.
Extraversion	.938	.886	.613	3.5985	.94497
Agreeableness	.957	.834	.756	3.5294	.83133
Conscientiousness	.951	.923	.594	3.6508	.85948
Neuroticism	.942	.854	.643	3.3566	.98722
Openness	.977	.912	.589	3.3353	1.06884
Sabotage	.973	.900	.632	3.1706	1.14741
Withdrawal	.948	.876	.645	3.0250	1.10962
Deviance	.941	.906	.745	2.9275	1.08512
Theft	.881	.879	.773	3.1318	.92924
Abuse	.929	.934	.591	3.0647	.74793

Source: Author compilation

The results as provided in table 2 above suggest that our survey adapted for the variables involved had a good level of reliability in this particular context since all Cronbach alpha and Composite reliability turned to be greater than the required value of 0.70. The variables also had good convergent validity as all AVE (Average Variance Extracted) turned out to be greater than 0.50. The construct validity is also good since all indicators including GFI, AGFI, CFI are greater than 0.90 and RMSEA is less than 0.05 and RMR is less than 0.08. The values are compared against the standard values as suggested by experts including Bagozzi, et al., (1999); and Hair, et al., (2010).

The mean values of personality profile indicate the average type of personality (M=3.65, SD=.85); neuroticism (M=3.35, SD=.98); and openness (M=3.33, SD=1.06). The mean values of counterwork dimension indicate lower level of counter work reported including sabotage (M=3.17, SD=1.14); withdrawal (M=3.02, SD=1.10); deviance (M=2.92, SD=1.08); theft (M=3.13, SD=.92); and abuse (M=3.06, SD=.74).

Table 3: Discriminant Validity

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Extraversion	.782	.624	.710	-.733	-.656	-.558	-.534	-.580	-.635	-.681
Agreeableness	.624	.869	.624	-.611	-.512	-.410	-.389	-.370	-.496	-.549
Conscientiousness	.710	.624	.770	-.614	-.533	-.552	-.467	-.474	-.615	-.665
Neuroticism	-.733	-.611	-.614	.801	.746	.450	.471	.460	.583	.761
Openness	-.656	-.512	-.533	.746	.767	.425	.416	.423	.509	.690
Sabotage	-.558	-.410	-.552	.450	.425	.794	.717	.730	.643	.573
Withdrawal	-.534	-.389	-.467	.471	.416	.717	.803	.882	.816	.486
Deviance	-.580	-.370	-.474	.460	.423	.730	.682	.863	.861	.500
Theft	-.635	-.496	-.615	.583	.509	.843	.616	.861	.879	.684
Abuse	-.681	-.549	-.665	.761	.690	.573	.486	.500	.684	.768

Source: Author compilation

Table 3 present discriminant validity related statistics. The discriminant validity is established when Square Root of AVE (values given in bold diagonally) are greater than the values in its representative rows and columns. This is in accordance with the guideline provided by Fornell and Larcker (1981). In our case, all bold values are greater than other values in its representative rows and columns as can be seen in table 3 above, so it shows that discriminant validity is present for variables in our study.

4.1 Hypothesis Testing

Table 4: Coefficients

Factor	Independent Variable	Estimate	S.E	CR	P Value	H. No	Remarks
Sabotage	<--- Extraversion	-.365	.131	-2.777	**	H1a	Supported
Sabotage	<--- Agreeableness	-.004	.120	-.030	.976	H1b	Not Supported

Sabotage	<---	Conscientiousness	-.410	.126	-3.257	***	H1c	Supported
Sabotage	<---	Neuroticism	-.020	.128	-.154	.878	H1d	Not Supported
Sabotage	<---	Openness	.081	.104	.785	.434	H1e	Not Supported
Withdrawal	<---	Extraversion	-.365	.132	-2.756	***	H2a	Supported
Withdrawal	<---	Agreeableness	-.017	.121	-.143	.886	H2b	Not Supported
Withdrawal	<---	Conscientiousness	-.188	.127	-1.485	.139	H2c	Not Supported
Withdrawal	<---	Neuroticism	.126	.129	.973	.332	H2d	Not Supported
Withdrawal	<---	Openness	.047	.104	.447	.656	H2e	Not Supported
Deviance	<---	Extraversion	-.525	.126	-4.169	***	H3a	Supported
Deviance	<---	Agreeableness	.053	.115	.462	.645	H3b	Not Supported
Deviance	<---	Conscientiousness	-.161	.121	-1.335	.184	H3c	Not Supported
Deviance	<---	Neuroticism	.036	.123	.294	.769	H3d	Not Supported
Deviance	<---	Openness	.053	.099	.532	.595	H3e	Not Supported
Theft	<---	Extraversion	-.260	.097	-2.695	***	H4a	Supported
Theft	<---	Agreeableness	-.037	.088	-.416	.678	H4b	Not Supported
Theft	<---	Conscientiousness	-.306	.093	-3.309	***	H4c	Supported
Theft	<---	Neuroticism	.147	.094	1.555	.122	H4d	Not Supported
Theft	<---	Openness	.045	.076	.591	.555	H4e	Not Supported
Abuse	<---	Extraversion	-.055	.062	-.894	.372	H5a	Not Supported
Abuse	<---	Agreeableness	.010	.057	.180	.857	H5b	Not Supported
Abuse	<---	Conscientiousness	-.232	.059	-3.893	***	H5c	Supported
Abuse	<---	Neuroticism	.298	.061	4.907	***	H5d	Supported
Abuse	<---	Openness	.151	.049	3.083	***	H5e	Supported

Source: Author compilation

Table 4 present coefficient results as presented above. It indicates that most of the dimensions of the Five-Factor model of personality bring negative and significant change in employee counter work behavior and its dimensions. For example, for the sabotage dimension, extraversion ($\beta=-.365$, $P<.05$); conscientiousness ($\beta=-.410$, $P<.05$) turned out to be significant while, agreeableness ($\beta=-.004$, $P>.05$); neuroticism ($\beta=-.020$, $P>.05$); and openness ($\beta=.081$, $P>.05$) were insignificant. For the withdrawal dimension, only extraversion ($\beta=-.365$, $P<.05$) turned out to be significant; while, agreeableness ($\beta=-.017$, $P>.05$); conscientiousness ($\beta=-.188$, $P>.05$); neuroticism ($\beta=.126$, $P>.05$); and openness ($\beta=.047$, $P>.05$) turned out to be insignificant.

For the deviance dimension, extraversion ($\beta=-.525$, $P<.05$) turned out to be significant; while, agreeableness ($\beta=.053$, $P>.05$); conscientiousness ($\beta=-.161$, $P>.05$); neuroticism ($\beta=.036$, $P>.05$); and openness ($\beta=.053$, $P>.05$) turned out to be insignificant.

For the theft dimension, extraversion ($\beta=-.260$, $P<.05$); conscientiousness ($\beta=-.306$, $P<.05$) were significant; while, agreeableness ($\beta=-.037$, $P>.05$); neuroticism ($\beta=.147$, $P>.05$); and openness ($\beta=.045$, $P>.05$) turned out to be insignificant.

Finally, for abuse dimension, conscientiousness ($\beta = -.055$, $P < .05$); neuroticism ($\beta = .298$, $P < .05$); and openness ($\beta = .151$, $P < .05$) turned out to be significant; while, extraversion ($\beta = -.055$, $P > .05$); and agreeableness ($\beta = .010$, $P > .05$) turned out to be insignificant.

4.2 Discussion

The objective of the present study was to test the influence of personality traits on employee counter work behavior. For this purpose, the Five-Factor model of personality is utilized which consists of dimensions including extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness. The five dimensions' model of employee counter work behavior is also utilized consist of dimensions including the sabotage, deviance, withdrawal, theft, and abuse. Results were based on a cross-sectional survey conducted among the staff of five selected NGOs operating in the social sector. Results show that extraversion and conscientiousness, bring a negative influence on employee counter work behavior. Whereas, neuroticism and openness bring positive influence on employee counter work behavior. Results for agreeableness turned out to be mixed. These results are supported by previous studies. For example, Bolton et al (2010) conducted a study about the influence of personality on employee counter work behavior and found that personality is influenced by Five-Factor model based dimensions. Other studies also found similar results including O'Neill et al (2011); Kozako et al (2013); and Witt et al (2004).

The first main result is that extraversion is negatively associated with employee counter work behavior dimensions. Generally speaking, extraversion is about being outgoing, adventure seeking, and self-confident (Bakker, et al 2002). Individuals having high score on extraversion are more social and is likely to be better controlling their behavior such as anger and stress (Salgado, 2002). Therefore, mostly, literature did not report positive association between extraversion and counter work behavior. However, study of Jensen-Campbell and Malcolm (2006) reported positive association between extraversion and counter work behavior of employees. Other studies also mostly found negative association between extraversion and counter work behavior which is similar to our results (e.g. O'Neill et al 2011; Witt et al 2004).

The other finding is that conscientiousness is negatively associated with employee counter work behavior. Conscientiousness dimension is about being organized, routine-oriented, and disciplined (Bakker et al 2002). Mostly, such individuals like to work in organized manner and do not involve in negative behavior. Literature mostly support a negative association

between conscientiousness and employee counter work behavior (e.g. Salgado, 2002; O'Neill et al 2011).

The third finding is that neuroticism is positively associated with employee counter work behavior. The neuroticism dimension is about being emotionally weak and easily losing control of one's emotional state (McShane & Glinow, 2017). Generally, speaking individuals having high score on neuroticism dimensions are emotionally weak and may involve in negative work behavior such as theft or vandalism. Literature mostly reported positive association between the both and thus support our finding (e.g. Kozako et al 2013; Berry et al 2007).

The fourth finding is that openness to experience is positively associated with employee counter work behavior. This dimension is about being experimental, adventurous in nature, original, imaginative, and creative (Bakker et al 2002). An individual who is adventurous and having experimental nature can easily move from positive behavior to negative behavior as part of the fun seeking behavior or adventure. Literature support that openness is mostly positive related to the counter work behavior and thus match with our findings (e.g. Bolton et al 2010).

Finally, we found mixed results for agreeableness dimension. This dimension is about being being compassionate, cooperative, and empathic type of behavior (Bakker et al 2002). We found mixed results but generally, literature support a negative association between agreeableness dimension and counter work behavior due to the very nature of the agreeableness dimension (e.g. Berry et al 2007; Salgado, 2002; O'Neill et al 2011). In sum, mostly, our results are matching with the findings of earlier work on the same topic.

5 Conclusion

The conclusion of the study is that personality traits based on the Five-Factor model of personality are important in shaping employee's counter work behavior. It can be concluded that personality dimensions can be used for predicting employee's counter work behavior. Individually, it can be concluded that extraversion and conscientiousness are negatively associated with counter work behavior; while, neuroticism and openness are positively associated with counter work behavior. The results can be associated with Five-Factor model based studies or Big Five personality model which mostly shows that personality is an important determinant of behaviors at workplace (Bakker et al 2002; Bolton et al 2010; John et al 2008). Furthermore, the findings can also be associated with Bandura (1977) social learning theory which states that an individual personality and resulting behavior is shaped by learning from the environment.

5.1 Recommendations

- The first recommendation is that the NGOs management may use the Five-Factor based personality dimensions as part of their recruitment & selection process. Appropriate tests can be used to judge candidate personality and for predicting a candidate's future counterwork behavior.
- The second recommendation is that the NGOs management may use the Five-Factor based personality dimensions for their current employees in order to make a prediction about the current employee's future counter work behavior.
- The third recommendation is that the NGOs management may provide employees appropriate support such as counseling in order to help employees overcome their counter work behavior.
- The fourth recommendation is that there must be a proper mechanism in place in an organization that helps reporting, investigation, and prevention of future counter work behavior.

5.2 Limitations

The study's key limitation include its small sample size based on 170 respondents only. Another limitation is that the study used a self-reported measure of counter work behavior which may not be a very good reflection of reality. Furthermore common method bias which cause variations in response by the use of same instrument (Podsakoff, Mackenzie, & Podsakoff, 2012). In other words, since we are collecting data on both independent and dependent type of variables from same respondents, so common method bias may be introduced in the data. This problem could be avoided if we have collected data on separate variables from separate respondents, however, due to the financial and time constraints, we restricted to same respondents. This fact need to be kept in mind while generalizing the results of the study.

5.3 Directions for Future Research

One direction for future researchers wishes to investigate employee personality and counter work behavior is that they may use data from different sources about employee personality and counter work behavior such as from managers and colleagues. The use of mediators such as trust on supervisor, organizational culture; or moderators such as employment tenure can also be investigated by a future researcher.

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